

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

Title	Security, Privacy and Quality Mechanisms for Hyper-Distributed Applications
Document Owners	UOWM
Contributors	ICE, UOWM, CERTH, DNET, ICCS, FDI, INNO, EITB, OSO
Dissemination	Public (PU)
Date	30/06/2025
Version	V1.0

Version History

Nr.	Date	Author (Organization)	Description
0.1	05/03/2025	Athanasios Liatifis (UOWM), Ross Campbell (ICE)	Initial Table of Contents (ToC)
0.2	12/03/2025	Athanasios Liatifis (UOWM), Ross Campbell (ICE)	Update ToC
0.3	20/05/2025	Athanasios Liatifis	Update ToC and deliverable structure
0.4	04/06/2025	Athanasios Liatifis, Manolis Skoularikis, Thomas Lagkas, Dimtris Pliatsios, Panagiotis Sarigiannidis (UOWM)	Update deliverable structure, include UOWM content
0.5	20/06/2025	Athanasios Liatifis, Manolis Skoularikis (UOWM)	Minor changes to UOWM contribution,
0.6	23/06/2025	Ross Campbell, Fareed Hussain (ICE)	Updates to Application Controller, and requirements analysis sections.
0.7	24/06/2025	Athanasios Liatifis, Dimitrios Pliatsios (UOWM)	Content integration and final text revisions
0.7	24/06/2025	Alexandros Nizamis (CERTH)	Peer review
0.7	25/06/2025	Petia Nikolova, Nadia Khan (DS4)	Peer review
0.7		Vesna Kobal, Jan Harej (Arctur)	Peer review
0.8	27/06/2025	Athanasios Liatifis, Dimitrios Pliatsios, Manolis Skoularikis (UOWM), Ross Campbell, Usman Wajid, Fareed Hussain (ICE), Haya Al Kassir, Manolis Kelaidis (FDI), Efsthios	Resolve review comments, integrate partners inputs

		Karanastasis, Evangelos Apostolakis, Vassiliki Lambropoulou (ICCS), Srdjan Krco, Dejan Drajić (DNET), Óscar Lázaro, Katia Lavin, Cristina Domínguez (INNO), Eneko Aguirre, Leonardo Hakim, Carla Sánchez, Ainhoa Gómez(Osoigo), Larraitz Eguren, Artzai Egiguren, Amaya Remon (EITB)	
0.9	30/06/2025	Ross Campbell (ICE)	Update Section 3.3 – Application Controller
1.0	30/06/2025	Athanasios Liatifis, Manolis Skoularikis, Thomas Lagkas, Dimitris Pliatsios, Panagiotis Sarigiannidis (UOWM)	Final version after addressing reviewers' comments and integrating partners updated input

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Acknowledgement

The ENACT project is funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission under Grant Agreement 101135423.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACPI	Advanced Configuration & Power Interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
APLPM	Application Policy Model
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Development
CIDR	Classless Inter-Domain Routing
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
DGM	Dynamic Graph Modeler
DRAM	Dynamic Random Access Memory
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
Gi	Gibibyte
HA	High Availability
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IP	Internet Protocol
IPMI	Intelligent Platform Management Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8S	Kubernetes
KW	KiloWatt
MS	Microseconds
NVML	NVIDIA Management Library
OPA	Open Policy Agent
RAPL	Running Average Power Limit

REST	Representational State Transfer
RTPOL	Runtime Policy
RX	Receive
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TX	Transmit
VM	Virtual Machine
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the security, privacy, and quality mechanisms designed for hyper-distributed applications within the context of the Horizon Europe project ENACT. It details the architecture, interfaces, deployment procedure, and documents the first implemented versions of three ENACT components: (1) the Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME), (2) the Application Controller (AC) and the (3) Application Policy Model (APLPM). Furthermore, the document introduces the ENACT Application-Level Adaptation Mechanisms and its core component, the Application Controller. The findings and specifications presented herein lay the groundwork for ensuring robust security, preserving user privacy, and maintaining high quality of service for hyper-distributed applications developed within the project.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a comprehensive review of the technical advancements achieved in the development of tools within the ENACT project, particularly those related to the objectives of Task 6.3: 'Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper Distributed Applications (Quantifications and Assessment)'. Specifically, it details the progress made in designing and developing tools and mechanisms aimed at ensuring the quality, security/privacy of hyper-distributed applications. These mechanisms are critical for enabling the adaptive and efficient scaling of distributed applications. The deliverable highlights any open issues encountered and outlines the planned future development directions for these tools, which address the unique challenges posed by the deployment of applications across multiple geographically dispersed sites characterized by high levels of complexity and scale. The deliverable also touches upon the quality and security monitoring architecture being explored and the development of policy models to maintain data integrity, confidentiality, and availability, while protecting against security threats.

1.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable is tightly related to other ENACT activities and objectives that fall under other Work Packages. The main relation of this deliverable is to WP6 tasks, namely T6.1 Design and Specification of ENACT Application Programming Model, T6.2 Application-Level Adaptation, Elasticity, Load Balancing and Energy Efficiency Characterization, T6.3 Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper Distributed Applications and T6.4 Software Development Kit (SDK). The technical objectives of WP6 are to design an application programming model and an SDK for developers to use during development phase of their applications and the development of application aware mechanisms that extend the traditional infrastructure-oriented orchestration standard approach.

The deliverable is also linked to other ENACT WPs and activities:

- WP2 deliverables, namely D2.1 'State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications', D2.2 'ENACT User and System Requirements', D2.4 'State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications - Final', D2.6 'ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Reference Architecture - Final' related to the state-of-art analysis and ENACT architecture definition.
- WP3 Tasks that are associated with the utilization of the components in the respective use cases.
- WP4 and WP5 Tasks, where components developed under the umbrella of these tasks closely interact with WP6 components to visualize, perform optimization or interact with other components using functionalities of WP6 components

1.3 Structure of the deliverables

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1 - Introduction** outlines the deliverable aim, structure and relation to other ENACT activities.
- **Section 2 - Requirements Analysis** provides an overview of core requirements related to three WP6 components, The Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine, the Application Policy Model and the Application Controller
- **Section 3 - Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper-Distributed Applications** provides the technical details, deployment steps and future work of three ENACT components. Each component corresponds to a dedicated subsection where the internal component architecture is presented, followed by the interfaces with other components and finally the deployment steps and next steps in terms of feature delivery and technical progress.
- **Section 4 - Release Summary** includes information related to repositories hosting the source code, the documentation and the container images of the developed components.
- **Section 5 - Conclusions** summarises the overall effort and provides an overview of next steps.
- **Appendices** consolidate the Kubernetes manifests, API functions and calls of the components documented in this deliverable.

2. Requirements Analysis

2.1 Requirements Analysis for Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine

The Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) plays a crucial role in monitoring distributed applications across the ENACT platform. It can efficiently collect telemetry metrics from all the deployed applications in the cluster, such as CPU and memory usage, network traffic, and storage usage. Consequently, it offers observability and policy enforcement across cloud and edge Kubernetes clusters. Furthermore, TDCME must detect potential policy violations in near real-time by monitoring communication patterns and resource access. This enables the early identification of unauthorized access or misconfigurations, which may compromise the security and/or integrity of the system.

To support integration and system-wide awareness, TDCME must provide mechanisms to publish collected metrics securely to shared data spaces, such as the ENACT Data Layer. These mechanisms should follow a unified data model to avoid schema conflicts and support API and query-based access with low latency. In case the direct collection of data is not possible, for instance, due to bandwidth or policy constraints, fallback methods such as inferred metrics or lightweight agents can be used. Furthermore, the system should adapt its polling rate based on application behaviour. For example, when an application shows abnormal patterns, the TDCME must increase monitoring resolution to capture more detailed traces and logs. This adaptive behaviour should not impose any overhead on the compute nodes. To this end, buffered metric processing and optimized polling strategies are utilized.

Additionally, administrators should be able to configure the storage location of collected data, thereby complying with internal policies and adapting to constraints such as limited bandwidth or organization rules about data storage. To support this, TDCME leverages storage abstraction and policy-aware volume scheduling. Also, it must ensure that its resource consumption remains minimal compared to the applications from which the respective metrics are collected. In this direction, the TDCME uses lightweight agents and, where needed, offloads processing to centralized or cloud services to reduce the utilization of resources in constrained nodes.

TDCME needs to incorporate telemetry alerts to inform administrators when there is a notable decline in node health or communication links. These alerts should be based on thresholds or dynamic baselines derived from historical data. Alerts must also be compatible with ENACT components and maintain accuracy by consistently validating the threshold with respect to the observed performance.

In addition, the system must offer a real-time topology view of the infrastructure, showing pod-to-pod communication paths across Kubernetes clusters. In order to handle this efficiently, TDCME

should use optimized Prometheus queries, stream updates, and leverage Cilium's capabilities, ensuring key ENACT components are whitelisted for traffic inspection. Finally, TDCME must maintain and expose a complete list of all collected metrics including node-level, pod-level, container-level, energy use, latency, and application metrics exposed by Prometheus. An API endpoint must be provided where users can retrieve this list. The metrics list must remain up to date as metrics are added or deprecated and transform internal representations into user-friendly formats. This transparency supports debugging, integration, and automated metric discovery across ENACT use cases.

The aforementioned functionality is reflected in the requirements below, also present in TDCME Gitlab¹:

C13.1 - Telemetry Data Collector shall be able to monitor all deployed distributed applications efficiently. Prometheus is used to obtain and collect cluster-level metrics and the newly developed API can efficiently communicate with all registered clusters. This offers cluster-wide monitor capabilities.

C13.2 - The Telemetry Data Collector shall be able to identify potential policy violation attempts in near real-time. During the M01-M18 period, ENACT policies were identified. TDCME will implement the corresponding translation of policy-to-alert functionality during the M18-M36 period.

C13.3 - Telemetry Data Collector shall be able to provide mechanisms to publish data to shared data spaces in a secure manner. TDCME employs sovity EDC connectors to register infrastructure-wide state and provide a historic view of the infrastructure and application state.

C13.4 - The Telemetry Data Collector should provide adaptive monitoring mechanisms that focus on monitoring distributed applications. Thanks to the cluster-level based monitoring, TDCME can fine tune each cluster to match specific monitoring

C13.5 - The administrator shall be able to specify the locations to place infrastructure data volumes. The administrator can properly configure TDCME to place data volumes in specific nodes or even to remote storage volumes (e.g. AWS S3 buckets).

C13.6 - The Infrastructure Monitor shall consume minimal resources compared to distributed application requirements and cluster available resources. TDCME has reached a mature state in terms of metrics collections and validate across multiple setups and Kubernetes distributions. During M18-M36 period benchmarking and comparison study against other solutions.

C13.7 - The Telemetry Data Collector shall provide alerts when there is a significant degradation of the nodes/communication links. This functionality is identified, documented and will be explored in M18-M36 period, focusing on Use Case applicability.

C13.9 - Provide a topology view of the underlying infrastructure. The initial version of the topology is developed. Some bugs were identified related to topology updates. During M18-M36 these issues will be resolved and finalised.

¹https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/telemetry-data-collector-and-monitoring-engine/-/issues/?sort=label_priority&state=opened&first_page_size=100

C13.10 - Include a list of metrics collected. TDCME documentation provides API calls, sample replies and description of data types.

2.2 Requirements analysis for Application Policy Model

The Application Policy Model enables administrators to define runtime policies that describe the envisioned runtime state from the developer's point of view. The Application Policy Model covers four major aspects of applications: (1) computing resources such as CPU and memory limits, (2) network configurations such as expected latency and bandwidth, (3) storage requirements such as type of storage technology and (4) locality of deployment across cloud and edge environments. By specifying these four aspects, a developer can accurately describe the desired environment where their application will operate optimally. Moreover, the Application Policy Model offers some additional parameters such as the underlying kernel version and accelerators and exposes certain aspects of the application to orchestrating services. Finally, the Application Policy model exposes certain security aspects of the application such as alignment with legislation and necessary encryption technologies.

To support the distributed and high-availability nature of these applications, the Application Policy Model should utilize high-availability database to store application metadata. The underlying database system should provide low response time and efficiently store these policies.

Application Policy Model descriptors should be easy to understand by humans but also easy to parse by software systems, while also validating a policy and rejecting it if not valid. This ensures that all policies associated with a distributed application are aligned with ENACT models.

Taking into account modern cloud environments where accelerators play a crucial role in application throughput, the Application Policy Model should allow applications to describe acceleration technologies that are used to increase total application throughput.

The aforementioned functionality is reflected in Application Policy Model requirements²:

C17.1 - The distributed application owner should be able to specify runtime policies that accurately describe the desired state of the application on runtime in terms of computing, networking, storage and locality of distributed application deployment. Using Custom Resource Definitions, owners/administrators are able to specify application deployment parameters, which ensures alignment with ENACT's performance standards.

C17.2 - A policy should be stored in a high-availability database and use efficient representation methods. Runtime policies are stored in Kubernetes cluster datastore (etcd), ensuring high availability and efficient query execution.

²https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-policy-model/-/issues/?sort=label_priority&state=opened&first_page_size=100

C17.7-The system should use regular expressions to enforce strict format validation (e.g., memory as Gi, latency as ms, power as KW) for all policy fields aligned with ENACT's specification. Validation checks have been implemented, which ensures that all fields comply to the expected units and formatting, which reduces the risk of misconfigurations.

C17.8-The system must validate application runtime policies for syntactic and semantic correctness before deployment to ensure conformance with ENACT's platform constraints on performance, energy, network, and security. It checks for schema and logical errors in order to reject deployments of non-compliant configurations.

C17.9-The system must not rely on hardware-specific features and must support deployment in both cloud and edge Kubernetes clusters within the ENACT ecosystem. The application policy model is hardware-agnostic, ensuring compatibility across heterogeneous cloud and edge environments within the ENACT platform.

2.3 Requirements analysis for Application Controller

The Application Controller must satisfy several critical requirements to fulfil its role within the ENACT architecture. Functionally, it is responsible for supporting runtime adaptation through container relocation, scaling, and resource allocation decisions. It must evaluate and enforce application behaviour policies, continuously monitor application cluster states and application runtime behaviour via telemetry feedback and supports compliance insights to other components and end users. As an intelligent control mechanism, the controller must respond rapidly to dynamic changes in cluster states or policy configuration.

Non-functional requirements are equally important. The component must exhibit high availability, as it governs adaptation behaviours that directly affect application continuity and correctness. It should also ensure low-latency communication with other ENACT modules to support timely adaptation. Secure operation is essential—particularly when exchanging sensitive data, telemetry logs, or compliance information. Additionally, the controller should be scalable to support an increasing number of applications upon pertaining cluster and deployment context spanning cloud and edge environment.

To ensure robust and intelligent management of containerised applications, the Application Controller must incorporate resilient telemetry acquisition mechanisms that combine data from the TDCME with internal fallback methods. This ensures uninterrupted monitoring even in the event of service disruptions. Beyond passive monitoring, it must also support synthetic monitoring, error tracking, root cause analysis, and alerting—enabling proactive, real-time observability and context-aware optimisation decisions. A detailed understanding of application structure is essential, requiring the ability to import and interpret Kubernetes and Docker Compose deployment descriptors to extract container topology and service relationships. Furthermore, the controller must continuously enforce user-defined application policies—including performance, availability, and behavioural constraints—triggering adaptations when deviations are detected to maintain

compliance and service quality. Finally, secure and authorised communication with other ENACT components is vital, necessitating integration with identity and access management systems such as Keycloak, in alignment with best practices in security and regulatory compliance.

The aforementioned functionality is reflected on Application Controller requirements³:

C02.1 – The Application Controller must be able to gather telemetry data for all the components of the application. Integration with TDCME api now complete, with fallback mechanisms for telemetry collection being developed for an event where communication is lost.

C02.2 – The Application Controller must be able to recommend turning off and on specific application containers or components. Work is currently ongoing in the development of mechanisms to request redeployment and configuration changes.

C02.3 – The Application Controller must be able to communicate with the ENACT Orchestrator. Initial discussions have taken place with the Orchestrator to define and collaborate on the development of the communication mechanisms between the Application Controller and Orchestrator.

C02.4 – The Application Controller must be able to suggest the movement of specific containers on different edge and cloud resources or change their deployment configuration to help with the application performance and energy consumption criteria. Initial mechanisms for the generation of redeployment requests has been developed based on policy model thresholds available, work is on-going for requests specific adaptation actions.

C02.5 – The Application Controller must be able to request changes to the resources allocated to one or more components/containers of the application. Initial mechanisms for the generation of redeployment requests has been developed based on policy model thresholds available, work is on-going for requests specific adaptation actions.

C02.6 – The Application Controller must implement telemetry acquisition mechanism that combines data from the TDCME with internal fallback methods to ensure uninterrupted monitoring of container and node-level metrics. Integration of TDCME api is complete, with work on-going to complete fallback mechanisms and assess together with TDCME data.

C02.7 – The Application Controller must support synthetic monitoring, error tracking, root cause analysis, and alerting functionalities to provide real-time observability and actionable performance insights. A suite of functions is being developed for the Application Controller, with a set of methods focusing on each of the above functionalities.

C02.8 – The Application Controller must support the import and interpretation of Kubernetes and Docker Compose deployment descriptors to extract application structure and container topology for adaptation

³https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-controller/-/issues/?sort=label_priority&state=all&first_page_size=100

decisions. Initial work has started on parsing the helm, and docker-compose files for application deployment.

C02.9 – The Application Controller must monitor and enforce user-defined application policies, including performance, availability, and behavioural constraints, as part of runtime decision-making. Several functions have been developed for the reading of defined policy model threshold, and assessing application metrics against this, with work on-going to finalise the processes for requesting redeployment.

C02.10 – The Application Controller must monitor and enforce user-defined application policies, including performance, availability, and behavioural constraints, as part of runtime decision-making. Work has been completed to monitor several aspects of the Application Policy Models with monitoring of parameters such as memory and CPU usage, development continues on monitoring and assessing the remaining parameters.

3. Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper-Distributed Applications

This section outlines the technical characteristics and progress of components developed under T6.2 'Application-Level Adaptation, Elasticity, Load Balancing and Energy Efficiency Characterisation' and T6.3 'Quality, Security and Privacy Policy Models for Hyper Distributed Applications ', focusing on observability and policy enforcement within the ENACT platform. The Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) offers a scalable observability framework that collects and exposes telemetry data from Kubernetes clusters, integrating technologies like Cilium, Hubble, and Kepler to monitor compute, network, and energy layers, whereas the Application Policy Model Validator enforces declarative policies for distributed applications by validating complex YAML specifications before orchestration.

Figure 1: ENACT Architecture

3.1 Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine

3.1.1 Design Approach

Figure 2: TDCME Conceptual Architecture

The **Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME)** is a set of open-source technologies for monitoring distributed systems and distributed applications. The tool is designed to scale across multiple remote sites, emphasizing on data locality as depicted in Figure 2. Metrics are collected from four main sources, namely (a) the Kubernetes cluster, (b) the underlying nodes (VM or physical nodes), (c) the network stack, (d) the distributed application itself [1]. By collecting metrics from these endpoints, other ENACT services and components can efficiently obtain information related to the state of the cloud continuum and the distributed application(s) running. To realise its goal, the TDCME leverages several open-source technologies, obtaining metrics from multiple infrastructure layers, namely, computing, networking and filesystem metrics of the underlying nodes. Due to the distributed nature of modern applications, TDCME is designed to operate on distributed environments, limiting data transfer between clusters. A summary of the tools and technologies the TDCME has adopted is summarized below:

- Cilium:** Cilium is an open-source, cloud-native networking solution that provides advanced networking, security and observability features in Kubernetes environments [1] by utilizing the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF), a powerful Linux Kernel technology [1]. When eBPF programs are executed directly within the kernel, Cilium enables dynamic interception, filtering, and manipulation of network traffic at multiple layers of the networking stack, allowing for efficient enforcement of network and security policies beyond the capabilities of traditional tools. Hubble which is built upon Cilium, delivers real-time insights into network flows, service-to-

service communication, DNS resolution metrics, and Layer 4/Layer 7 telemetry [3]. When combined, they provide detailed network metrics to Prometheus for monitoring and analysis.

- **Kepler:** Kepler allows monitoring and optimizing power consumption in Kubernetes environments [1]. It leverages software counters, custom machine learning models and the Cloud Native benchmark suite to offer accurate energy estimations and detailed metrics of power consumption at the pod and container level. Kepler integrates into the existing Prometheus pipeline, exposing energy consumption metrics through standard HTTP endpoints, which Prometheus then scrapes. The Model Server component of Kepler's architecture facilitates the selection and training of appropriate power estimation models tailored to specific hardware configurations [1]. As a result, the system can increase the energy efficiency through this approach while maintaining compatibility with different system architectures. The system depends on Kepler to achieve energy-aware orchestration and sustainability monitoring. To achieve energy monitoring, Kepler employs eBPF programs to extract process-level resource utilization metrics directly from the Linux kernel. Also, it leverages with hardware APIs such as Intel's Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) [2] for CPU and DRAM power measurements, NVIDIA's Management Library (NVML) for GPU power, and Advanced Configuration & Power Interface (ACPI) or Intelligent Platform Management Interface (IPMI) for platform-level power data. The collected energy metrics enable real-time decision making and support the enforcement of runtime policies for energy efficiency.
- **Kubelet Node metrics:** Node-level metrics are exposed through the Kubelet, which is the agent running on each node in a Kubernetes cluster. Kubelet provides metrics about the pods that are hosted on a node and also provides metrics for the nodes of the cluster. cAdvisor is integrated into the Kubelet and exposes container metrics on the HTTP server. All the above metrics are essential for monitoring the health and resource utilization of containerised workloads, as the exposed metrics include CPU, memory, disk usage, and network throughput, to detailed insights into node health conditions, including readiness status and resource availability. These metrics are essential for monitoring and managing the health, performance and resource utilization of the containerized workloads in the cluster.

The aforementioned tools and technologies generate events and capture metrics originating from low-level system components like the operating system Kernel. There are several tools available that can capture these events, such as Zabbix or the Elasticsearch Stack, however, they are characterised by increased operational complexity or require customized solutions to achieve the desired behaviour. Moreover, modern solutions such as Prometheus have known wide adoption. To this end, the TDCME adopts Prometheus [9] as the main tool for collecting metrics across the Edge to Cloud continuum. Prometheus scrapes metrics directly from Kubernetes nodes, Cilium/Hubble metrics, and Kepler for energy usage insights. Prometheus is used as a metrics aggregator, ensuring robust and high-resolution time series data collection for each registered cluster. Prometheus also exposes metrics via HTTP endpoints that can be periodically scraped by other tools.

Figure 3: TDCME Implementation

TDCME exposes a RESTful API based on Flask framework where administrators can register new clusters, request metrics of microservices or nodes and obtain a topology view. Compute metrics such as CPU utilization, memory consumption and filesystem load are provided on a per Pod or per Node level [9]. The Monitor API also exposes network information such as node to node delay across the cloud continuum, typical metrics such as packets per second, bits per second on a per Pod or per Node level. Leveraging Cilium's Service Mesh feature, additional metrics are available, such Pod-to-Pod interactions and L7 observability, including protocol specific metrics such as HTTP methods, response codes, and request paths, which enables visibility into service-to-service traffic. Furthermore, energy metrics can be obtained, offering an approximation of the cycles a container has consumed in a given time frame. Finally, through processing the Cilium events, TDCME can create a service graph, where interactions between pods and the delay, as measured by Cilium, are represented as a graph. TDCME's modular and micro-service based approach allows the creation of additional microservices built on top of existing and well-established frameworks, offering enhanced telemetry services.

3.1.2 Interfaces

TDCME exposes a suite of RESTful APIs that provide structured access to real-time telemetry collected from Kubernetes-managed infrastructure. These APIs serve as a lightweight and standardized interface through which both internal platform components and external orchestration systems can query system level metrics. The exposed endpoints cover a wide range of observability domains, including CPU and memory utilization, filesystem and network activity, as well as energy consumption. These metrics are made available at both the pod and node levels, enabling detailed visibility across the full deployment topology.

In addition to basic resource telemetry, TDCME also features a dedicated topology API that provides a real-time view of pod-to-pod communication within the cluster. This topology graph is dynamically

generated and can effectively capture logical relationships between application components. This is critical for understanding interdependencies, detecting communication bottlenecks, and supporting policy-aware orchestration. Finally, TDCME enables comprehensive situational awareness across complex and multi-service environments by combining infrastructure and topology data. The following subsections present the interfaces that integrate with TDCME, such as the Dynamic Graph Modeler, Application Controller and Data Access and Sharing interface.

3.1.2.1 Dynamic Graph Modeler Interface

The Dynamic Graph Modeler (DGM) creates a visual representation of application communication within the ENACT system. To achieve this, it uses enhanced flow level telemetry from the TDCME, which leverages Cilium and Hubble to capture detailed pod-to-pod interactions and network behaviour. TDCME aggregates data such as CPU and memory usage, network traffic, and filesystem utilization directly from the monitor API. This process allows the DGM to generate real-time graphs of microservice dependencies, helping in network optimization and policy management.

3.1.2.2 Application Controller Interface

The Application Controller obtains information about the present deployment environment through the TDCME. The controller uses real-time metrics from applications, together with the nodes that they are hosted on to make deployment decisions that understand their current context. The controller checks TDCME for target node runtime constraints about CPU availability, memory capacity, and network bandwidth before starting any deployment. Also, the controller performs validation by querying endpoints - to identify suitable environments. Through this process, the Application Controller implements placement policies that deploy applications on nodes with sufficient capacity to meet operational needs, thus optimizing cluster resource utilization and maintaining performance standards.

3.1.2.3 Data Access and Sharing Interface

TDCME can interact with the Share Data Spaces component by publishing selected telemetry events or structured datasets. This allows metrics and topology data to be shared across services, tenants, or administrative domains, enabling cross-functional collaboration and federated analytics. Such integration supports advanced use cases, including multi-tenant monitoring, platform-wide anomaly detection, and lifecycle management across distributed application layers.

These interactions are facilitated through well-defined HTTP interfaces and can be discovered through the Kubernetes-native service discovery mechanisms. All APIs are designed to be stateless and follow standard REST design principles, ensuring they can be consumed by other ENACT components or third-party tools. The communication model emphasizes interoperability, modularity, and extensibility, in line with the microservice architecture of the ENACT platform. Consequently, TDCME not only provides critical visibility into system behaviour, but also acts as an enabling layer for orchestrated, data-driven operations within the ENACT cloud continuum.

3.1.3 Implementation

TDCME deployment provides system-wide scalable modular observability solutions for distributed cloud and edge environments. The TDCME agents are installed through Helm charts into Kubernetes clusters under the 'enact' namespace to provide smooth integration with existing ENACT services. The system architecture uses open-source technologies such as Cilium for network telemetry and Kepler for energy profiling and Prometheus for metrics aggregation in a cloud-native design. The deployment process simplifies operational complexity so developers and system integrators can deploy observability services through configuration without manual changes to infrastructure settings. All services of TDCME are deployed under the enact namespace. This approach simplifies the deployment and management of the telemetry component. TDCME may require some elevated privileges to collect metrics.

3.1.3.1 Cilium Installation and Configuration

Cilium goes beyond the classic approach of Container Network Interface (CNI) plugins, offering advanced networking, security and load-balancing capabilities through a rich and Kubernetes-compliant Network Policies framework [10]. The ENACT platform uses Cilium as its main CNI plugin to provide high-performance networking capabilities and security policy enforcement and deep observability features. The deployment is designed for multi-cluster environments using Cluster Mesh and integrates Hubble for real-time telemetry and traffic flow monitoring across all registered clusters. The command below lists the command to install Cilium CNI using the cilium command line tool [4]:

```
cilium install --version="1.16.4" \  
--set cluster.name="cloud1" \  
--set cluster.id=1 \  
--set ipam.operator.clusterPoolIPv4PodCIDRList="10.10.0.0/16" \  
--set sctp.enabled=true \  
--set hubble.enabled=true \  
--set hubble.tls.enabled=false \  
--set hubble.relay.enabled=true \  
--set hubble.ui.enabled=true \  
--set hubble.metrics.enableOpenMetrics=true \  
--set hubble.metrics.enabled="{dns,drop,tcp,flow,port-  
distribution,icmp,httpV2:exemplars=true;labelsContext=source_ip\,source_namespace\,source_w  
orkload\,destination_ip\,destination_namespace\,destination_workload\,traffic_direction}" \  

```

```
--set global.hubble.enabled=true \  
--set global.hubble.listenAddress=":4244" \  
--set global.hubble.ui.enabled=true \  
--set envoy.enabled=true \  
--set prometheus.enabled=true \  
--set operator.prometheus.enabled=true \  
--set cni.chainingMode="none"
```

The command above will install the Cilium CNI version 1.16.4 using the Helm package manager. The administrator must specify the cluster name and cluster ID, a unique number in the range 1 to 255. Moreover, the administrator must specify the Pod Classless Inter-Domain Routing (CIDR) list. This value should match the Kubernetes cluster CIDR range used for allocating IP addresses to Pods. The command also enables Hubble observability framework and configures the metrics exposed by Hubble and the Hubble UI. Finally, the Prometheus exporter is enabled, while the CNI chaining Mode is disabled, rendering Cilium as the only CNI managing the cluster.

3.1.3.2 Prometheus Stack Deployment

Prometheus acts as the telemetry aggregation layer across all ENACT components. It collects metrics from Kepler, Cilium, and node exporters, exposing them via standard endpoints. Helm is used for deploying and configuring the stack under the enact namespace. The command below deploys Prometheus to the cluster:

```
helm install infra prom-stack --namespace enact --create-namespace
```

3.1.3.3 Kepler Deployment

Kepler is deployed under the enact namespace to collect detailed energy and hardware metrics at the container level. It enables Prometheus to scrape energy data via a service monitor, helping to enforce ENACT's energy-aware orchestration objectives.

Firstly, the label that will be used as a parameter in the installation of kepler must be extracted using the following command:

```
kubectl get prometheus --all-namespaces -o yaml | grep -A5 "serviceMonitorSelector"
```

After the extraction of the label, the following command is used to install kepler:

```
helm install kepler kepler/kepler --namespace enact --create-namespace \  
--set serviceMonitor.enabled=true \  

```

```
--set serviceMonitor.labels.release={label}
```

3.1.3.4 TDCME API Services

All TDCME services are packaged as a Helm chart. Currently, there are two services developed: (1) the monitor-api service, which exposes the TDCME API and (2) the topology API, which creates a container graph. The API enables the registration/removal of clusters across the cognitive cloud continuum and provides the API for obtaining metrics. The following command is used to deploy the TDCME services:

```
helm upgrade --install tdcme-api ./api/chart/ --namespace enact --create-namespace
```

```
helm upgrade --install tdcme-api-topology ./topology_exporter/chart/ --namespace enact --create-namespace
```

Detailed listing of the API and sample responses are presented in Appendix 1: TDCME API.

3.1.4 Development Status

The first half of the projects aimed towards the identification of agents capable of collecting network, compute and energy metrics while also working on diverse cloud environments was the first step during the initial component design and the development of API for other tools to utilise. The selected agents, described in previous sections, directly address the unique operational requirements of ENACT within multi-cluster environments and can operate in restricted environments where access to low-level infrastructure state is not available due to policies (e.g. cloud operator environments). An API is also developed, exposing metrics from all registered clusters by communicating with Prometheus instances in a unified manner. Custom endpoints (e.g., topology) aiming to simplify interaction with TDCME have been developed and are available. These endpoints aggregate data from multiple agents in a single request-response, eliminating the need for consequent messages and possible delivery of outdated data. Finally, TDCME stores the infrastructure state to Share Data Space, offering historic data to other components. Section 4 provides details related to source code, documentation and the latest version of the component available.

As of the submission date, the Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine is functional and operational in terms of deployment and collecting metrics. The next phase of development will focus on developing alerting mechanisms and monitoring of Quality-of-Service indicators, primarily focusing on ENACT Use Cases. The Addition of application-level metrics and traces is investigated and will be included in the next phase of development. The API will be extended to support dynamic loading of monitoring/alerting and dynamic registration of QoS metrics that are derived from application-level metrics and traces. Finally, application logs integration will be explored. The logs will be incorporated, and the API will be extended to support dynamic alerts using these logs.

3.2 Application Policy Model

3.2.1 Design Approach

The Application Policy Model is an adaptation and implementation of the ENACT Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) Application Model. In the context of the ENACT project three types of models are defined: (1) the Telemetry model responsible for defining the data captured, (2) the Application model that describes an application desired state and (3) the Resource model that specifies an infrastructure asset characteristic. Solutions such as Open Policy Agent (OPA) [1] offer mechanisms to specify resource limits, tagging of namespaces, resource access control etc., however, they do not offer any mechanism for developers to specify how their applications behave [11]. Using the Application Policy Model application developers have a means of defining how their application operates and what is the desired runtime environment in order to operate optimally and securely [12].

The Application Policy Model specifies Runtime Policies are yaml-based descriptors that specify a distributed application's desired state in terms of infrastructure setup, resources availability, acceleration technologies and placement of resources across a cognitive compute continuum. Developers and administrators can specify the desired runtime state of their application, thus providing the application an optimal environment consequently leading to higher quality of services to users. Infrastructure managers can leverage this knowledge to optimally deploy containerized applications and minimize potential redeployments due to resource stagnation of nodes or unbalanced deployment during peak utilization hours.

The Application Policy Model consists of three complementary tools as depicted in Figure 4: (1) the Kubernetes Custom Resource Definition (CRD) manifests that offer a cloud native and Kubernetes-compliant method for defining such policies, (2) a validator tool for developers to validate runtime policies and (3) a Kubernetes operator to manage the custom resource objects. Figure 5 provides a technical implementation of the Application Policy Model, where existing Kubernetes components are utilised. This ensures compliance with existing approaches and

Figure 4 High-level view of Application Policy Model

CRDs offer a powerful mechanism to extend the Kubernetes API with user-defined resource types, thus providing new functionality and offering more versatility. Each CRD formally specifies the schema and validation rules for its corresponding custom resource, ensuring data integrity and consistency across all instances. The API extension enables developers to use existing, well-established tools and technologies to deploy applications. CRDs allow administrators and developers to introduce custom objects that perfectly match their application's unique requirements or infrastructure components. CRDs are often paired with custom controllers, known as Kubernetes operators, that continuously monitor instances of these custom resources for changes in their desired state.

Figure 5: Application Policy Model component

3.2.2 Interfaces

The Application Policy Model defines and manages rules that describe how an application should run in a Kubernetes cluster. These rules include application needs in terms of desired CPU and memory capacity, type of storage technologies desired and network characteristics such as jitter and delay. Moreover, certain security aspects such as placement of resources can be specified and legal frameworks that may be applicable. Other components in the ENACT platform, such as the Application Controller, retrieve these rules and make sure that each app runs in a setup that meets its requirements.

3.2.2.1 Application Controller Interface

The Application Controller talks to the Application Policy Model through an interface. It queries the Application Policy Model to retrieve the policy of the respective application. These policies define how the application should be deployed and operated, based on runtime conditions such as hardware availability, network performance, and security requirements. After retrieving the needed policy, the controller evaluates whether the current or desired application state aligns with the specified rules. This allows the controller to make sure that the application is set up correctly, maintains compliance, and adapts to changing runtime environments.

3.2.3 Implementation

The Application Policy Model consists of two components. The Application Policy Model Kubernetes Custom Resource Definitions and a Kubernetes operator to monitor and enforce them. These are implemented to align with ENACT's goal of declarative, policy-driven orchestration and platform compliance.

3.2.3.1 Custom Resource Definitions

To support Kubernetes-based environments, the Application Policy model is offered as a CRD named 'RuntimePolicy'. To avoid naming conflicts the CRD is grouped under the 'enact.eu' group. This provides a structured way to define detailed operational and resource requirements for applications deployed in a Kubernetes environment, ranging from specific CPU features, GPU models, and network characteristics such as bandwidth and latency, placement of data storage volumes. Moreover, security parameters, privacy considerations (such as the nature of data), energy consumption, and required software environments are also supported enabling developed to fully express the runtime characteristics of their application to management systems and where their workloads should execute based on performance, hardware, and regulatory needs.

3.2.3.2 Kubernetes Operator

To manage RuntimePolicy objects effectively, the custom Kubernetes operator is designed following the well-established Operator pattern, which essentially encapsulates human operational knowledge into software. It constantly monitors the cluster for newly registered RuntimePolicy objects and updates to existing ones, ensuring the desired state is consistently enforced. Beyond this, it exposes a crucial API for other services to query and potentially influence runtime policies for specific distributed applications.

At its core, the operator implements a control loop (also known as a reconciliation loop), which is the heart of any Kubernetes controller or operator. This loop's primary responsibility is to observe the current state of RuntimePolicy objects and associated resources in the cluster and then drive the actual state towards the desired state expressed within the RuntimePolicy specification.

3.2.4 Deployment Methodology

The Application Policy Model offers a validation service for Yaml-based configuration policies throughout the cloud continuum. It is intended for integration into the ENACT platform and can be implemented in both development and production Kubernetes clusters via Helm charts in the enact namespace. Built using Python, the validator utilizes a minimal collection of open-source technologies, including Flask as the API interface and PyYAML for configuration file parsing. Its stateless architecture eliminates the need for specific hardware, making it ideal for both resource-limited edge environments and resource-intensive cloud environments. This component uses the Kubernetes Operator pattern via the Kopf framework to monitor and validate *ApplicationRuntimePolicy* custom resources in real time. As a result, the validator functions natively within the Kubernetes control loop, empowering ENACT's event-driven orchestration workflows. For secure operation in production environments, it is advisable to place the service behind an ingress controller or API gateway with TLS encryption, authentication, and rate limiting. This protects the validator from unauthorized access and misuse. The deployment is achieved via helm for declarative, version-controlled deliveries. Runtime configuration can be adjusted through environment variables, Kubernetes ConfigMaps, and mounted schema files. All services are implemented under the enact namespace to maintain seamless integration with ENACT's ecosystem.

Helm Installation

The following command installs the validator under the enact namespace and connects it to the Kubernetes API via Kopf to watch and validate ApplicationRuntimePolicy CRs:

```
helm upgrade --install runtimepolicy-enact-eu ./chart/ \  
--namespace enact --create-namespace
```

Docker Image deployment

For local testing, the validator can be deployed as a Docker container using the following commands:

```
docker build -t application-policy-model-validator:latest .  
docker run -p 8080:8080 application-policy-model-validator:latest
```

3.2.5 Development Status

At the point of submission, a subset of core features of the Application Policy Model component have been completed. Development thus far focused on the definition, validation, and structural foundation of runtime policies for distributed applications. Policies can now be stored in a high-

availability storage database using efficient formatting, providing persistence and efficient query execution, which is required for production-grade scenarios.

Implementation of strict format validation for all policy fields using regular expressions, ensuring that parameters like memory, latency, and power consumption adhere to ENACT's standards, has been successful. Additionally, the CRD and the structure of runtime policies have been completed, providing a solid base for policy creation and management. Section 4 provides details related to source code, documentation and the latest version of the component available.

Besides the above successfully implemented functionalities, development continues in several areas. Current efforts are focused on building an API interface that will allow application administrators to define and submit runtime policies describing parameters such as computing requirements, network constraints, storage utilization, and deployment locality. Also, via the API, administrators and components will be able to retrieve and inspect policies. Improvements are being made to the validation logic, including semantic and syntactic validation, which ensures that policies are compliant to ENACT's CCC model. Efforts are also underway to remove any hardware-specific dependencies to make sure that the policy model can operate seamlessly across a wide range of Kubernetes distributions and setups.

The next phase of development will prioritize the expansion of the operator to support full lifecycle management of runtime policies. Although not all features are complete, the Application Policy Model includes key operational characteristics and forms a stable component for ongoing and future development. Its integration with the Application Controller plays a critical part in the project's vision for declarative, policy driven application management across the cloud-to-edge continuum.

3.3 Application Controller

3.3.1 Design Approach

The Application Controller is a core component within the ENACT Platform architecture and situated within the App Development Layer of the ecosystem. The component plays a crucial role in the enabling of runtime application adaptation across the Cloud Computing Continuum (CCC). The component's architectural design supports the dynamic management of containerized applications through monitoring of telemetry data, enforcement policy rules and AI compliance, and coordination adaptation decisions with the ENACT Orchestrator and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) Agent. The objective of the Application Controller is to ensure that applications deployed on the ENACT CCC are managed efficiently during deployment and operation, while adhering to compliance and policy requirements, and reacting to environmental and operational changes in real time.

The Application Controller is implemented as Java application following the Spring Boot framework and is developed as a microservice that is deployed in the ENACT CCC, a Kubernetes managed environment. Internally, the Application Controller consists of several interrelated systems, each supporting a distinct aspect of the adaptation process. The Application Adaptation Engine forms the

core of the system’s decision-making capability and includes modules such as the Relocation Requester, the Resource Allocation Requester, and the Container Enabler. These modules are responsible for initiating the relocation of application components, requesting additional resources from the DRL Agent, and activating or scaling containers, respectively. Supporting the Application Adaptation Engine is a suite of Application Adaptation Strategies, which provide logic for specific adaptation goals such as load balancing, elasticity, and energy efficiency. These strategies inform how adaptation requests are generated and prioritized.

The component also provides an Application Reconciler Engine, that is responsible for interacting with the AI Act Compliance Check service, and the Application Policy Models. The Application Controller interfaces with the AI Act Compliance Check Service to assess whether the proposed application state and adaptations conform to regulatory and ethical frameworks, and it queries the Application Policy Model to retrieve active policies that define acceptable application behaviours under various runtime conditions. Together, these capabilities allow the Application Controller to function as a policy and data-driven control point for deployed applications.

The Application Controller architecture is included below in two key figures. Figure 5 depicts the architecture of the Application Controller including expected interaction with external ENACT components, while Figure 6 shows only the internal architecture of the component, focusing on the interaction between the modules and functions of the Application Controller.

Figure 6: Application Controller Architecture

Figure 7: Application Controller Architecture - Internal

3.3.2 Interfaces

The Application Controller exposes and consumes several interfaces to fulfil its responsibilities within the ENACT architecture. It provides RESTful endpoints for external components to request application adaptations and retrieve compliance feedback, enabling programmatic interaction using secure and standardised formats. Internally, it consumes telemetry, policy, and application data from other ENACT modules to inform its decision-making processes. It sends adaptation requests to the DRL Agent, coordinates redeployment through the Orchestrator, and receives operational constraints from the Application Policy Model. Additionally, it interacts with the AI Act Compliance Checker to evaluate the legality and fairness of ongoing system behaviours. All communications occur via RESTful APIs using structured JSON payloads, secured through HTTPS and token-based authentication. A sample of the endpoints for which development has been completed has also been included in Appendix 3, [Table 4](#), which is also reflected below in [Figure 8](#), where an example of functions is presented. The Application Controller also employs Kubernetes service discovery to dynamically locate its dependent services at runtime.

Figure 8: Application Controller Example Workflow

3.3.2.1 Application Policy Model Interface

The Application Controller communicates with the Application Policy Model to retrieve current operational policies and behavioural rules that govern application execution. These policies define constraints related to performance, availability, thresholds, and other quality attributes. The controller queries this component at regular intervals or upon specific triggers (e.g., configuration updates or detected violations) to obtain the latest policy set. This interface ensures the controller always operates in alignment with the defined objectives and constraints, enabling it to monitor compliance and trigger adaptation actions when violations occur. Data exchange occurs via secure RESTful endpoints, and policies are represented using structured, machine-readable formats such as JSON.

3.3.2.2 TDCME Interface

The Application Controller integrates with the TDCME to acquire real-time telemetry data required for informed decision-making. This includes metrics, logs, events, and alerts related to both container- and node-level operations. The TDCME serves as the primary source of operational observability, allowing the controller to assess system health, detect anomalies, and evaluate the impact of previous adaptations. The controller accesses this data through well-defined RESTful APIs, supporting secure, token-authenticated access. In addition, fallback mechanisms are implemented within the controller to ensure continuity in telemetry acquisition in case of TDCME unavailability, enhancing overall resilience.

3.3.2.3 AI Act Compliance Check Interface

The Application Controller communicates with the AI Act Compliance Check to provide support to the developers of AI models and solutions based on AI to comply with the AI Act. The module analyses relevant documentation provided by the AI-based solution as well as the associated training data to provide recommendations regarding the risk allocation and the changes/updates needed to get the application supporting documentation in line with the relevant clauses of the AI Act. Data exchange occurs via secure RESTful endpoints, and recommendations are represented using structured, machine-readable formats (JSON).

3.3.3 Implementation

Deployment of the Application Controller follows a microservice-oriented approach and is carried out using Kubernetes. The component is packaged as a Docker container, which includes the Spring Boot application and all required dependencies. This container is deployed into a Kubernetes pod, and the pod definition includes service specifications and configuration references. A configuration map is used to externalise and manage runtime configuration parameters such as telemetry thresholds, polling intervals, and API endpoint definitions. Sensitive settings such as authentication

tokens or database credentials can be injected using Kubernetes secrets. The component's service account and permissions are governed by Kubernetes Role Based Access Control policies to ensure that it interacts with only the approved resources within its namespace.

The Application Controller integrates with the platform's observability stack and provides Prometheus-compatible metrics endpoints for system monitoring. Logs are collected and aggregated using the Kubernetes logging subsystem, enabling centralised analysis and debugging. The deployment process is designed to support rolling updates and automatic restarts, ensuring minimal downtime during maintenance or configuration changes.

With regards to the steps requirements for deployment of the Application Controller in the Enact ecosystem, a version of the ENACT deployment sequence diagram has been included below in Figure 7, focusing in on the overall deployment steps related to the Application Controller. As shown, the deployment process starts via the SDK, in which the application owner will configure their app deployment, selecting the required jars from the APM. The user will then request deployment via the SDK, through a local deployment of the Application Controller. From this point, the Application Controller will send a request to the DRL Agent to request the optimal deployment schedule for the configured application. Once this has been provided, the Application Controller will send the deployment schedule to the Orchestrator and request deployment on the ENACT CCC. Following the deployment of the user application, alongside an instance of the Application Controller, the AC instance will then monitor and manage the deployment.

In the deployment management phase of the AC lifecycle, the AC will first query the Application Policy Models defined by the application owner, and check these against application telemetry data obtained from the TDCME. In addition, the AC will have fallback mechanisms for the collection of telemetry data in the event communication with the TDCME is lost. The AC will then check compliance of the user application with AI regulations through the AI Act Compliance Checker. Alongside these processes, the AC will also facilitate any access requests through to the ENACT Data Layer and retrieve forecasted telemetry data required by the AC. Based on the monitoring and measurement of telemetry data against policy model threshold, the AC will then implement adaptation actions, via requests for redeployment through to the DRL Agent.

Figure 9: Application Controller Deployment Sequence Diagram

3.3.4 Development Status

At the time of submission, the Application Controller is in an active development phase and progressing according to the ENACT roadmap. Development has been focused on two main areas: performance monitoring and container state optimization. A total of seventy functions have been defined for performance monitoring, of which twenty-six are currently implemented. These completed functions focus on the ingestion and analysis of telemetry data, as well as the generation of adaptation feedback in response to observed performance issues. In the area of container state optimization, twenty-seven functions have been scoped, and six have been developed so far. These initial functions provide baseline capabilities for tasks such as container restarts and basic load distribution. Section 4 provides details related to source code, documentation and the latest version of the component available.

The first phase of development has been focused on finalizing the system architecture, implementing core telemetry processing, and establishing initial communication with the Orchestrator and Data Manager. The next phase is concentrating on integration with the Application Policy Model and the compliance checking module, along with the enhancement of adaptation strategies. Subsequent milestones will expand the range of optimisation techniques and establish a secure compliance

reporting workflow. The final phase is reserved for testing, documentation, and packaging the component for public release.

The Application Controller is a partially completed component although key functional building blocks are operational. Its current features allow it to process telemetry input, and generate adaptation actions to enforce application policies. While current development has focused on the internal methods to query the TDCME and Policy Models, in the next phase, focus will be placed on integration with the Orchestrator and AI Layer, while providing the necessary endpoint for interaction with the AC. The next stages of development will also significantly expand its optimization logic and integrate compliance capabilities. The component is aligned with the ENACT project's goals and has been designed from the outset to support public review, reusability, and interoperability across distributed environments in the cloud-to-edge continuum.

4. Release Summary

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine	Monitor API	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/telemetry-data-collector-and-monitoring-engine/-/tree/main/monitor-api/api
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/telemetry-data-collector-and-monitoring-engine/-/tree/main
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	Prometheus Cilum Kepler
		Version	1.0.0
	Topology exporter	Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/telemetry-data-collector-and-monitoring-engine/-/tree/main/monitor-api/topology_exporter
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	-
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	Cilium Hubble

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Application Policy Model		Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-policy-model
		Binaries	

		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-policy-model
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Application Controller		Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-controller
		Binaries	Not yet available.
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/application-controller/-/blob/main/README.md
		Docker Image	Not yet available.
		Dependencies	Application Policy Model DRL Agent Orchestrator

5. Conclusions

This deliverable documented the TDCME, the Application Policy Model, and the Application Controller components that were developed in the context of the ENACT project. In more detail, the TDCME provides API endpoints, leveraging several advanced technologies, such as Cilium, Hubble, and Kepler. This offers enriched metrics and detailed overview of both infrastructure and containerised application state. The Application Policy Model offers definition of runtime state and is aligned with cloud-native paradigm. It is deployed as a Kubernetes microservice and undertakes the continuous monitoring of runtime policies, always ensuring that the policies are validated prior to their deployment and other ENACT components are notified once these policies are updated. The Application Controller is a key element for runtime adaptation and provides core functionalities, including performance monitoring, container state optimization and through close interaction with ENACT orchestration layer and compliance checks.

These components are integrated in terms of functionality and act as the first fully integrated version of the ENACT quality, security, and observability mechanisms, including their interfaces, deployment methodologies, and core functions which are operational and validated in controlled environments. As the project continues, more updates are to be implemented, including advanced adaptation strategies, management of the runtime policies, and extended telemetry support such as application-level metrics, alerting functions, QoS indicators. Finally, further enhancements and fine-tuning of these components are expected throughout the project's duration. Of note, these improvements will be documented in D6.4 'Security, Privacy and Quality Mechanisms for Hyper-Distributed Applications – Final', which is due in M36.

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Appendix 1: TDCME API

Table 1: TDCME APIs

Category	Description	Example
pod/{pod}/cpu	returns the CPU utilisation of {pod} Pod with respect to total node CPU resources.	<code>{"metrics":{"local":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.0221"]}], "remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.0184"]}]}}, "name":"pod-name", "resource":"pod"}</code>
pod/{pod}/memory	returns the Memory utilisation of {pod} Pod with respect to total node memory.	<code>{"metrics":{"local":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.1368"]}], "remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.1363"]}]}}, "name":"pod-name", "resource":"pod"}</code>
node/{node}/cpu	returns the CPU utilisation of {node} node with respect to total node CPU resources.	<code>{"metrics":{"local":[], "remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.0123"]}]}}, "name":"node-name", "resource":"node"}</code>
node/{node}/memory	returns the Memory utilisation of {node} node.	<code>{"metrics":{"local":[], "remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.2696"]}]}}, "name":"node-name", "resource":"node"}</code>
node/{node}/fs	returns the Filesystem space utilisation of {node} node.	<code>{"metrics":{"local":[], "remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.2081"]}]}}, "name":"node-name", "resource":"node"}</code>
node/{node}/network	returns the total TX/RX network metrics of {node} node.	<code>{"metrics":{"remote":{"cluster-name":{"rx":[{"value":[timestamp,"73041.02"]}], "tx":[{"value":</code>

		<pre>[timestamp,"143504.76"]]}]}}, "name":"node-name", "resource":"node"}</pre>
namespaces/{namespace}/pods	returns all pods under the {namespace}.	<pre>{"namespace":"namespace-name","pods":{"local":["pod-name"],"remote":{"cluster-name":["pod-name"]}}}</pre>
nodes	return all registered nodes.	<pre>{"local":["node-name"],"remote":{"cluster-name":["node-name"]}}</pre>
topology	return the Pod topology graph.	<pre>{"PodCount": 2,"Pods":{"podName":"pod-name-1","podNamespace":"namespace-name","podNode":"node-name","podInteractions":{"cluster-name/pod-name-a":1.0}},{"podName":"pod-name-2","podNamespace":"namespace-name","podNode":"node-name","podInteractions":{"cluster-name/pod-name-b":1.0}}}</pre>
pod/{pod_name}/{container_name}/metrics	returns CPU and memory metrics of a container inside the specified pod.	<pre>{"container":"container-name","metrics":{"local":{"cpu":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.0436"]}], "memory":{"value":[timestamp,"1707061248"]}}}}</pre>
pod/{pod_name}/energy	returns the energy consumption of the specified pod.	<pre>{"containers":{"local":{"container-name":276852.98},"remote":{"cluster-name":{"container-name":247862.13}}},"pod":"pod-name","total":{"local":276852.98,"remote":{"cluster-name":247862.13}}}</pre>

latency/{source_node}/{destination-node}	returns the latency between two Kubernetes nodes across the Edge-to-Cloud continuum.	{ "metrics":{"local":[],"remote":{"cluster-name":[{"value":[timestamp,"0.0006487"]}]}}, "source_node":"node-name", "target_node":"node-name" }
--	--	--

Cluster Registration/Removal

TDCME enables users to dynamically register and remove Kubernetes clusters through its Monitor API. Clusters are registered using authenticated HTTP requests that supply metadata such as cluster name and Prometheus service NodePort. This capability ensures scalable telemetry federation across edge-to-cloud deployments.

Table 2 TDCME registration and deletion of a cluster

Command	Description	Output
<pre>curl -X PUT http://<api-node- ip>:32554/clusters \ -H "Content-Type: application/json" \ -d '{ "cluster_name": "<cluster- name>", "host": "http://<remote- node-ip>:<prometheus- service-NodePort>" }'</pre>	Cluster registration	{ "message":"Cluster 'cluster- name' stored." }
<pre>curl -X DELETE "http://<api- node- ip>:32554/clusters/<cluster- name>"</pre>	Cluster removal	{ "message":"Cluster 'cluster- name' removed." }

Appendix 2: Application Policy Model Custom Resource Definition

RuntimePolicy CRD

The following block of code contains the RuntimePolicy CRD in .YAML format. It defines the structure and allowed fields for RuntimePolicy objects within the Kubernetes cluster:

Table 3 Application Policy Model Kubernetes Custom Resource Definition

```
apiVersion: apiextensions.k8s.io/v1
kind: CustomResourceDefinition
metadata:
  name: runtimepolicies.enact.eu
spec:
  group: enact.eu
  preserveUnknownFields: false
  scope: Namespaced
  versions:
    - name: v1alpha1
      served: true
      storage: true
      schema:
        openAPIV3Schema:
          type: object
          properties:
            spec:
              type: object
              properties:
                performance:
                  type: object
```

```
properties:
  cpu:
    type: object
    properties:
      family:
        type: string
      instructions:
        type: array
      items:
        type: string
    cores:
      type: object
      properties:
        min:
          type: integer
        max:
          type: integer
    hardware:
      type: object
      properties:
        gpu:
          type: object
          properties:
            model:
              type: string
            memory:
              type: string
            tensorUnits:
              type: integer
```

```
fpga:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    gates:  
      type: integer  
    interfaces:  
      type: array  
      items:  
        type: string  
  nic:  
    type: object  
    properties:  
      speed:  
        type: string  
      supportedTechnologies:  
        type: array  
        items:  
          type: string  
  ram:  
    type: object  
    properties:  
      capacity:  
        type: string  
      timings:  
        type: string  
  dataStorage:  
    type: object  
    properties:  
      storageMediumType:
```

```
    type: string
  volume:
    type: string
  locations:
    type: array
    items:
      type: string
  network:
    type: object
    properties:
      capacity:
        type: object
        properties:
          bandwidth:
            type: string
          latency:
            type: string
          jitter:
            type: string
  security:
    type: object
    properties:
      encryption:
        type: string
  privacy:
    type: object
    properties:
      dataNature:
        type: array
```

```
  items:
    type: string
energy:
  type: object
properties:
  consumption:
    type: string
  greenEnergyMix:
    type: number
technicalDetails:
  type: object
properties:
  developmentEnvironment:
    type: array
    items:
      type: string
os:
  type: array
  items:
    type: string
executionEnv:
  type: object
properties:
  runtime:
    type: array
    items:
      type: string
libs:
  type: array
```

items: type: string scope: Namespaced names: plural: runtimepolicies singular: runtimepolicy kind: RuntimePolicy shortNames: - rtpol
--

Appendix 3: Application Controller – REST Endpoints

Table 4: Application Controller APIs

Category	Description	Example
/tdcme/topology-api/topology	Pulls the latest pod topology from Elasticsearch—no input needed. It should return the pod count, detailed pod data, and their communication links. Make sure the response format is correct and handles errors like missing data or connection issues.	<pre>{ "podCount": 1, "Pods": [{ "podName": "World/Host", "podNamespace": "", "podNode": "", "podIP": "", "podvEth": "", "workloads": "", "podLabels": {}, "since": "2025-04-09T16:00:00.000Z", "communications": { "cloud1/enact-248.ic4e.uk/elasticsearch-master-0": 1, "cloud1/enact-248.ic4e.uk/metricbeat-kube-state-metrics-5db55bfff7-qksbr": 1, "cloud1/enact-248.ic4e.uk/metricbeat-metricbeat-metrics-fd848d75c-q7x2x": 1, "cloud1/enact-248.ic4e.uk/coredns-668d6bf9bc-qcm25": 1, "World/Host": 1 } }] }</pre>

/tdcme/monitor-api/nodes	An endpoint to fetch local and remote nodes from Elasticsearch. The response should include a list of local nodes and remote nodes object—empty if no remote nodes are found. Ensure the data format is correct and handle errors gracefully if data is missing or inaccessible.	<pre>{ "local_nodes": ["enact-248.ic4e.uk", ""], "remote_nodes": {} }</pre>
/tdcme/monitor-api/pod/{pod_name}/energy	An endpoint that takes a pod name as a path variable and fetches its Kepler energy metrics from Elasticsearch. The response must follow a given format and handle errors for missing or invalid pod names. If remote metrics aren't available, return an empty {} for the "remote" field.	<pre>{ "metrics": { "local": { "energy_metric": 0.0, "pod_name": "elasticsearch-master-0", "timestamp": "2025-04-09T16:36:18.212Z" }, "remote": {} }, "pod_name": "elasticsearch-master-0", "resource": "kepler_energy" }</pre>
/monitorApplicationPerformance/api/metrics/generateOptimizationSuggestions	This function generates optimization suggestions based on performance metrics, energy consumption insights, and threshold violations. It helps in automated resource tuning and energy-efficient computing.	<pre>["Consider scaling CPU resources", "Optimize memory usage for better efficiency", "Investigate high energy consumption areas", "Recommendation: Address High CPU load", "Recommendation: Address Memory limit exceeded"]</pre>
/monitorApplicationPerformance/api/metrics/calculateEnergyEfficiency	The calculateEnergyEfficiency() method processes container performance metrics and calculates energy efficiency based on the provided data.	<pre>{ "Energy Consumption Score": 0.24607812980621346 }</pre>
/monitorApplicationPerformance/api/metrics/suggestDynamicAdaptation	This function provides dynamic adaptation strategies for containerized environments by analyzing real-time performance metrics and detected anomalies. It helps in	<pre>["Trigger: Investigate anomalies"]</pre>

	auto-scaling, resource reallocation, or load balancing based on system conditions.	
/api/policyModelCompliance/check	This feature adds a REST API that checks if a Kubernetes node meets the minimum CPU usage threshold (4 cores) using real-time nanocore metrics from TDCME. It returns a compliance confirmation, or a violation message based on the node's CPU utilization.	<p>HTTP 200 OK</p> <pre>{ "nodeName": "enact-248.ic4e.uk", "compliant": false, "violations": ["CPU usage 1.31 cores is below minimum threshold of 4 cores"] }</pre> <p>HTTP 400 Bad Request</p> <p>Scenario: Invalid or unknown JSON fields (e.g., resource_typex)</p> <pre>{ "type": "about:blank", "title": "Bad Request", "status": 400, "detail": "JSON parse error: Unrecognized field 'resource_typex'..." }</pre>